

METAPHORIC PERCEPTIONS OF 4TH GRADE STUDENTS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL ON THE CONCEPTS OF ATATÜRK, WAR OF INDEPENDENCE, AND REPUBLIC

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Abstract:

To determine the perceptions of the students in primary school on important concepts / values in cultural, historical and social context is of great importance in determining the views of students about these values. In this regard, in this present study, it is purposed to determine the metaphorical perceptions of the 4th grade students on the concepts of Atatürk, War of Independence, and Republic. The sample of the research structured according to the basic qualitative research method consists of 4th grade students studying in Denizli province. The stratified sampling method was applied to determine the sample of the study. Data of the research conducted with 91 fourth grade students in primary school were collected by open-ended questionnaire designed by the researcher. The data of the study were collected by the researcher, and the data were initially categorized and then analysed. In the analysis of the data, the percentage of consensus was analysed as the reliability analysis, and a reliability ratio of 0.81 was obtained for three questions. By analysing the data through inductive content analysis, the metaphors were first coded and then themes / categories were generated from codes. The findings were also supported by quotations. The codes obtained at the end of the study were visualized with the help of an academician from the department of art teaching, and the perceptions of the group on Atatürk, War of Independence, and Republic were visualized. According to the results of the research, it was concluded that the students perceived Atatürk as hero, star, saviour, and moon; War of Independence as independence and freedom; and Republic as freedom, shield, flag, and moon.

Keywords: primary school, metaphor, Ataturk, republic, war of independence

1. Introduction

There are certain people, facts or events that countries give importance to both in historical and cultural context. These people, facts and events are considered to be of

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historical importance for that country, as well as a value attributed by citizens. In the context of Turkey, Mustafa Kemal Atatürk was an important role model in terms of both the gain of independence and stepping into new age through the revolutions. Mustafa Kemal Atatürk pioneered to establish a new country in the place of the collapsed Ottoman Empire and struggled for independence through War of Independence. And then, he brought Turkey to the level of contemporary civilizations by making the breakthroughs needed by the public in the education, economy, political, and social fields that the country needed. Similarly, War of Independence is an important process for Turkey. Turkish War of Independence was an important war in terms of not only re-establishing Turkey independently by getting rid of the imperialist domination and persecution, but also the liberation of other Eastern nations from imperialist domination and persecution. Kemal Atatürk, the leader of this universal meaningful war, with his approaches revealed by him for the liberation of Turkey so as to be a fully independent country, has been honoured to be the leader of the national liberation wars of the Eastern nations with the national state plan (Oral, 2018, p. 3). After War of Independence, Atatürk made a gradual transition from the Caliphate to the Republic and declared the republic on 29 October 1923. In this context, the concepts of Atatürk, War of Independence, and Republic are important facts for the citizens in the country. For students, such fundamental facts are important in terms of culture, history, and value. When the statement, in article 2 of the Basic Law of National Education (1973), *“The general objective of the Turkish National Education is to raise all members of the Turkish Nation as citizens dependent on Atatürk’s revolution and principles and the nationalism of Atatürk expressed in the Constitution; adopting, protecting, and developing the national, moral, human, spiritual, and cultural values of the Turkish Nation; loving their family, country, and nation and always trying to glorify them; aware of his / her responsibilities towards Turkish Republic, which is democratic, secular, social state of law, and based on human rights and basic principles at the outset of the Constitution.”* has been taken into consideration, it is seen that the concepts of Atatürk and Republic are the general aims of national education. In this regard, it can be expressed that the concepts of Atatürk, War of Independence, and Republic are both important and valuable for the citizens in Turkey.

When we look at the definitions of what the value is, according to Celikkaya (1996, p. 168), the value is every kind of perception, thought, behaviour, rule or worth accepted, adopted, and sustained by society, belief, ideology, or people; and originating from social, human, ideological or divine. Oxford (2018) defines the value as something held to deserve; the importance, worth, or usefulness of something. The behaviours are directly or indirectly guided by values. While the children gain the values in the family and school, they reflect these values to the learning process (Saglam, 2016, p. 728). In this regard, the concepts of Atatürk, War of Independence, and Republic have value for the students. The cultural values in schools are presented to students within the scope of values education. Values and values education are emphasized especially in life sciences and social studies curricula; in other courses it has taken place within the hidden curriculum in Turkey’s primary schools (Demirel, 2009). Values education is

defined by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) as educational efforts for children and young people to explore and develop positive values and to advance according to their potential. As a concept, “value” refers to the principles that constitute judgments through which the individuals determine objects, people, ideas, situations, and behaviours as good-bad, right-wrong, desired-undesirable, and etc. (Eğitim-Sen, 2015). In the early years of the child, the environment, the events experienced under the effect of the environment, and the amount of stimulus in the environment have an important role in terms of mental development (Yavuzer, 1996). It is an education level that covers between 1st and 4th grades, namely 6-10 years of age. The students in this level begin to acquire the basic characteristics such as attitude, value, and personality they will use in their future lives. As a matter of fact, the positive factors affecting the child during this period are important in structuring the personality of the child. People represent knowledge in three ways, and they emerge in three ways. According to Bruner (1964), these are animated representation, iconic representation, and symbolic representation (Schunk, 2009, p. 342). Animated representation: It includes motor behaviour and manipulation of the environment. The movements such as cycling and knotting are mostly represented by muscle movements. The stimulus are called by the movements that lead to them. For the toddlers, the ball, which is the stimulus, is represented as something that moves and bounces. Iconic representation: It explains mental images independent from movement. Children acquire the ability to think about the objects that are not physically present. They can transform the objects in their minds and begin to think of the object separately from the movements that can be done with it. According to Çelen (1993), the iconic representation can be interpreted as the organization of selective perception and imagery of events or the transformation of the perceptual space into the earth, present and qualitative structures and their images. Symbolic representation: It uses symbol systems to encode information. These systems enable the person to understand abstract concepts and turn them into symbolic information as a result of verbal instruction. Symbolic systems represent information through their remote and optional features. The students who acquire animated, iconic, and symbolic representations can internalize the values needed and turn them into conceptual representations through analogies. The simplification of such values to different concepts or phenomena is called metaphor.

Metaphor “refers to the conceptual mapping and metaphoric expression to an individual linguistic expression, such as dead-end street, which is sanctioned by mapping” (Lakoff, 1993, s. 7). The term “metaphor” is composed of a combination of Latin and Greek meta (beyond, extreme) and pherein (move, undertake) (Inam, 2008, p. 43). In fact, metaphor is used instead of the term simile, which means to move beyond the term. Similarly, TLA (2018) defines metaphor as simile. Metaphors enable the synthesis of the ideas in the right brain by using the possibilities of consecutive thinking ignored by the left brain (Heidorn, 2001). Whereas Guiraud (1994) defines the meaning that people have in mind and has entered into words as literal meaning, he defines the new meanings by assuming the meaning of another word in one or more aspects as metaphor. Cameron

(1999, p. 8) identifies metaphor as the extraordinary features of language and thought. Shaw and Mahlios (2008) describe metaphor as a cognitive tool that organizes information. Metaphors help us explain a new concept based on a familiar concept (Ocak and Gündüz, 2006). In particular, it is important for the students in primary school to reach new concepts by using preliminary information in concept development. Metaphor is a powerful mental mapping and modelling mechanism for individuals to comprehend and construct their own worlds (Arslan and Bayrakçı, 2006, p. 103). Tompkins and Lawley (2002) describe the functional properties of metaphors as follows: Explaining a concept by using analogies, using a different concept in defining a concept, interpreting a concept from a different perspective, and seeing a concept in a different dimension than the one in which it is. According to Lakoff and Johnson (2005, p. 304), the features of metaphors are as follows: Metaphors are essentially conceptual; metaphoric language is secondary. Conceptual metaphors are based on the experiences arising from daily life. Abstract thought is largely metaphoric, although not entirely. Metaphoric thought is always available in the human mind and is often unconscious. Abstract concepts are deficient without metaphors. For instance, love is not love without such metaphors as magic, attraction, madness, joining, exaggeration, etc. Our conceptual system is not entirely consistent since the metaphors used to reason about concepts can be inconsistent. Individuals provide their experiences through the inferences supplied through metaphor.

A metaphor is used to identify the different aspects of a phenomenon and allows us to look at this phenomenon from a wider perspective. (Arnett, 1999). In this context, the determination of the metaphors of the students towards certain values will contribute to a wider view of the perspectives of the students. Metaphors are a multi-directional image. Like analogues, they are non-word to word comparisons, and they are used to make the content effective (Gentner and Wolff, 2000, p. 297). It is not a metaphor to explain any concept with a synonym; however, it is the process of describing the phenomenon with different concepts similar to this concept. Metaphoric concepts are similar since they contain similar features and relationships, combine these features, and create a new concept or understanding (Ortony, 1980, p. 186). According to Strenski (1989), metaphors shape the attitudes of individuals, thus direct the behaviors. Since metaphors against the basic values will affect their attitude towards those values, the discovery of metaphors also leads to the determination of their attitudes. According to Ahkemoğlu (2011, p. 12), metaphor is used to reveal the styles of teachers and students to create their own experiences and representations, to increase awareness of the students related to the key concepts and issues, to develop the teachers professionally by exposing the experiences of the students in language learning activities and situations through student metaphors. James (1960) describes the metaphor as a movement of the mind used in the discovery of reality and the experiences acquired within it. Steen (1994) states that metaphor is a cognitive mechanism that is effective in the formation of the conceptual world and that metaphor has become the most interesting situation especially in the social sciences. Since the basic subject of social sciences is human, determining the metaphors used by people in

understanding the world is important both for people's attitudes and for their point of view. According to Lakoff and Johnson (2005), human beings can only make sense of the world they live in through metaphors. The metaphor phenomenon that is so important is not only a matter of the students but also the teachers. In teacher education, metaphors are a tool in the process of education and in the determination of modern educational approaches (Vadeboncoeur and Torres, 2003, p.88). As a result, the fourth grade students can manage certain mental schemas and values or important concepts with metaphorical perceptions. Determination of how the students perceive and correlate important values such as Atatürk, Republic, and War of Independence is of importance in both determining the attitudes of students towards these phenomena and identifying their perspectives towards these phenomena.

In this regard, it has been aimed to determine the metaphoric perceptions of the fourth grade students about Atatürk, War of Independence, and Republic. For this purpose, the following sub-questions have been generated.

1. What are the metaphorical perceptions of the fourth grade students in primary school on Atatürk?
2. What are the metaphorical perceptions of the fourth grade students in primary school on War of Independence?
3. What are the metaphorical perceptions of the fourth grade students in primary school on Republic?

2. Method

2.1 Model

This research is structured in accordance with the qualitative research design. Qualitative researchers try to understand how people interpret their experiences, how they interpret their worlds, and how they make sense of their experiences (Merriam, 2013, p. 5). The model was implemented by selecting basic qualitative research among qualitative research methods. All qualitative research is about how meaning is constructed and how people make sense of their lives and worlds. The primary task of the basic qualitative research is to reveal and interpret these meanings (Merriam, 2013, p. 24).

2.2 Study Group

The population of the study is composed of the fourth grade students in the Denizli province and its districts. In this context, a study group was formed by taking a section from the population. In the scope of the study, stratified sampling method was applied in sample selection. The purpose of creating a sample based on stratified sampling is not generalization. On the contrary, it is to find out what kind of partnerships and similarities exist among the different situations (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2008, pp. 108-109). In stratified sampling, the population is divided into independent groups called as stratify, and a random sample is selected from each group (Christensen, Johnson and Turner, 2015, p. 167). In this context, the schools included in the sampling were

classified as low, medium and high in terms of their socio-economic structure. The socio-economic levels of the schools are named as low, middle and upper in the light of the information obtained from Denizli Pamukkale District National Education Directorate. Three schools were selected from each socio-economic level. A semi-structured questionnaire was applied to 139 students. 48 questionnaires were excluded from the study group due to incomplete fulfilment or incomplete understanding, and data analysis was performed with data obtained from 91 students. 52 of the participants were female, and the rest 39 were male.

2.3 Data Collection Instrument

Semi-structured interview is a common method of collecting data that is predetermined by the researcher, or that new questions can be asked according to the issues encountered during the interview (Güler, Halıcioğlu and Taşgın, 2015, p. 115). In this regard, a semi-structured interview form generated by the researcher was implemented. In the preparation of the form, the literature was first reviewed. In the light of the obtained information, the questionnaire prepared according to the students was shown to 3 classroom teachers in the context of relativity. Subsequently, feedback was obtained from 2 Turkish teachers about the spelling and dictation mistakes of the form. The questionnaire formed upon the feedback was applied to 12 fourth grade students in primary school, and a preliminary study was conducted. After the preliminary study, a personal information section was added to the form, and the final version of the semi-structured interview form was prepared. The form consists of 3 questions and personal information section.

2.4 Data Collection

Metaphors and analogies can be a powerful way of connecting with readers of qualitative studies, but some analogies offend certain readers. For this reason, metaphors and analogies should be chosen with the sensitivity of how the depicted people will feel and how the intended audience will react (Patton, 2014, p. 504). In this context, both the questions and the answers to the questions were read carefully. Since Atatürk is a key figure for Turkey, careful examination of the questions and the answers is important. The data were applied to the schools after the necessary permissions were obtained by the researcher. After explaining the purpose of the form and how to apply it, the students are asked to fill in the forms by giving required time.

2.5 Data Analysis

In the study, inductive content analysis method was implemented for data analysis. Content analysis is used to identify and quantify the existence of words, concepts, themes, idioms, characters or sentences in one or more texts (Seggie and Bayyurt, 2015, pp. 253-254). In the content analysis, also called thematic analysis, the researcher focuses on analytical techniques to search for themes and patterns within the data (Glesne, 2013, p. 259). Within the scope of the research, another researcher was asked for assistance in data analysis. The qualitative data were transcribed and read line by

line by the researchers. In this process, the content analysis was implemented to the data, and open-coding method was applied. During Open coding the data are broken down into small parts, closely examined, and compared for similarities and differences, and questions are asked about the phenomena as reflected in the data (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). The codes related to each other were combined to reveal the themes, and interpretations were generated. Control coding not only helps with definitive clarity but also assists in good reliability control (Miles and Huberman, 2015, p. 64). To reveal the consistency of the codes identified in the study, an agreement percentage was calculated for each question. In this calculation, the formula "Reliability=Agreement/Disagreement+Agreement x 100" was used (Miles and Huberman, 2015). By using this formula, an agreement percentage was obtained for each question. The reliability coefficient for the first question codes was 0.75, for the second question codes 0.92, for the third question codes 0.82. Metaphor analysis allows for a multifaceted research perspective for a variety of reasons: 1) Influence information processing. 2) Making confidential information reliable and accessible. 3) They are holistic representatives of understanding and knowledge. 4) Examples of common behaviors. 5) It reflects social and cultural understanding processes. 6) Quantitative and qualitative approaches can be combined. (Moser, 2000).

3. Findings

The following process was pursued so as to analyze each sub-question in the research:

- 1) Identification of codes: At this stage, metaphors of the students were tabulated by showing them through frequencies. Each of these frequencies refers the codes related to the sub-questions.
- 2) Identification of themes: At this stage, themes were formed by combining the similar codes, and each theme is shown with its frequencies.
- 3) Sub-codes related to the themes are shown and supported by quotations.
- 4) The codes for each sub-question are combined and a pool of different codes is created. Pencil drawings containing the elements in all codes related to these codes were prepared by getting assistance from a researcher with a PhD degree in Department of Art Teaching.

The first sub-question of the research is "What are the metaphorical perceptions of the fourth grade students in primary school on Atatürk?", and the metaphors given by the students related to this sub-question are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Metaphors generated by the students related to the phenomenon of Atatürk

Metaphor	f	Metaphor	f
Homeland	3	President	2
Republic	1	Fire and water	1
Traffic sign	2	Hawk	1
Brave	7	Sword	1
Patriot	2	Nation	1
Savior	6	Star	7

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Hero	7	Dictionary	1
Family	1	Archer	1
Independence	1	Ditch	1
Bee	1	Machine	1
Tank	1	Guide	1
Leader	4	Flag	4
Door	1	Moon	6
Pioneer	1	Warrior	1
Sun	2	Home	1
Candle	1	Author	1
Grape leaf	1	Torch	3
Ant	1	Mirror	1
Assembly	2	Father	2
Pencil	3	Black and white film	2
Angel	1	Gun	1
Book	1	Obstacle	1
Total		91	

When Table 1 is examined, the metaphors created by the students regarding the concept of Atatürk can be seen. The most used metaphors are hero (7), star (7), savior (6), moon (6) and leader (4). Considering the metaphors in Table 2, five categories can be mentioned for the concept of Atatürk. These are Atatürk in the context of the Guide, Atatürk in the context of the Savior, Atatürk in the context of the Military, Atatürk in the Political context, and Atatürk in the context of Personality. The categories prepared by using metaphors are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: The themes (categories) and metaphors related to the phenomenon of Atatürk

Categories	Metaphors	Number	Percentage (%)
Atatürk in the context of the guide			
	Family	1	
	Leader	4	
	Pioneer	1	
	Pencil	3	
	Book	1	
	Traffic sign	2	
	President	2	
	Candle	1	
	Star	7	
	Guide	1	
	Moon	6	
	Mirror	1	
	Torch	3	
	Total	33	%35
Atatürk in the context of the savior			
	Homeland	3	
	Patriot	2	
	Independence	1	
	Flag	4	

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	Door	1	
	Sun	2	
	Nation	1	
	Ditch	1	
	Father	2	
	Home	1	
	Obstacle	1	
	Total	19	%20
Atatürk in the context of the military			
	Savior	6	
	Tank	1	
	Grape leaf	1	
	Archer	1	
	Machine	1	
	Hawk	1	
	Sword	1	
	Warrior	1	
	Black and white film	2	
	Gun	1	
	Total	16	%21
Atatürk in the political context			
	Republic	1	
	Fire and water	1	
	Assembly	2	
	Total	4	%4
Atatürk in the context of personality			
	Brave	7	
	Hero	7	
	Bee	1	
	Ant	1	
	Angle	1	
	Dictionary	1	
	Author	1	
	Total	19	%20
All categories	Total	91	%100

Considering the categories related to the concept of Atatürk (Table 2), it is observed that the students refer to the guiding aspect of the concept of Atatürk in general (35%). This is followed by Atatürk categories in the context of personality and savior with 20%.

Examples of the metaphors of the students for the concept of Atatürk are as follows:

- Atatürk is like a traffic sign for me because he always shows us the right way.
- Atatürk is like a brave man for me because he bravely saved our country from the enemies.
- Atatürk is like a president for me because the president is the leader.
- Atatürk is like fire and water for me because when he gets angry, he is like fire; he is like water when he calms down.

- Atatürk is like a sword for me because he saved Anatolia from the enemies thanks to his sharpness.
- Atatürk is like a hawk for me because he does not hurt the public, but he will be like a raptor, showing its claw to the enemy.
- Atatürk is like a homeland for me because if he wasn't, the homeland wouldn't be.
- Atatürk is like a star for me because he always shines, and shines never ends.
- Atatürk is like a dictionary for me because solutions are endless for him.
- Atatürk is an archer for me because he's forward-thinking, and he shoots everything in full force.
- Atatürk is like a ditch for me because no one can beat him.
- Atatürk is like a bee for me because he is very hard working and successful.
- Atatürk is like an ant for me because he is as eager as an ant.
- Atatürk is like a tank for me because no enemy can beat him.
- Atatürk is like a flag for me because he always ruled us like a flag above us.
- Atatürk is like a pencil for me because he always writes the truth.
- Atatürk is like a black and white film for me because he turned our country from black to white.
- Atatürk is like a candle for me because he illuminates the darkness.
- Atatürk is like grape leaf for me because it symbolizes peace.

The drawing of the concept of “Atatürk” based on the metaphors of the students is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The drawing of the concept of “Atatürk”

The second sub-question of the research is “What are the metaphorical perceptions of the fourth grade students in primary school on War of Independence?”, and the metaphors generated by the students about this sub-question are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Metaphors created by the students about the phenomenon of War of Independence

Metaphor	f	Metaphor	f
Freedom	5	Independence	5
Turk	1	Foundation	3
Computer game	1	Chess	2
Sandglass	1	Tree	1
Eye	1	Flame	2
Light	2	Writing	1
Sun	2	Book	4
Waterfall	1	Clock	1
Water	3	Respect	1
Human	1	Stone	2
Lesson	3	Mind	1
Pilot pen	1	Gift	1
Bomb	2	Group	1
Football match	1	Blood	2
Eraser	1	Sacrifice	1
Notebook	2	Memory	1
Star	2	Mother	1
Moon	1	Black paper	1
Sand	1	History	2
Miracle	1	Resurrection	2
Shadow	3	Demolished Houses	1
Life	1	Peace	2
Olive branch	3	Flag	3
Epic	3	Rain	1
Terrible	1	Companion	1
Belief	3	Power	1
Total		91	

When Table 3 is examined, the metaphors developed by the students about the concept of the War of Independence are seen. The most used metaphors are freedom (5), independence (5) and book (4). Considering the metaphors in Table 4, there are generally six categories of the concept of the War of Independence. These are War of Independence in the context of Independence, War of Independence in the context of War, War of Independence in the context of Victory, War of Independence in the context of Peace, War of Independence in the National context, and War of Independence in the context of the Losses. The categories prepared by using the metaphors are demonstrated in Table 4.

Table 4: The themes (categories) and metaphors related to the phenomenon of War of Independence

Categories	Metaphors	Number	Percentage (%)
War of Independence in the context of Independence			
	Freedom	5	
	Light	2	
	Sun	2	
	Notebook	2	
	Star	2	
	Flag	3	
	Resurrection	2	
	Mother	1	
	Independence	5	
	Foundation	3	
	Total	27	%30
War of Independence in the context of War			
	Computer game	1	
	Bomb	2	
	Sand	1	
	Lesson	3	
	Power	1	
	Rain	1	
	Group	1	
	Stone	2	
	Chess	2	
	Total	14	%15
War of Independence in the context of Victory			
	Eraser	1	
	Miracle	1	
	Shadow	3	
	Waterfall	1	
	Epic	3	
	Gift	1	
	Writing	1	
	Tree	1	
	Total	12	%13
War of Independence in the context of Peace			
	Olive branch	3	
	Peace	2	
	Mind	1	
	Respect	1	
	Total	7	%8
War of Independence in the National context			
	Water	3	
	Moon	1	
	Belief	3	
	Companion	1	
	History	2	
	Turk	1	

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	Memory	1	
	Book	4	
	Total	16	%17
War of Independence in the context of the Losses			
	Sandglass	1	
	Eye	1	
	Human	1	
	Football match	1	
	Life	1	
	Pilot pen	1	
	Terrible	1	
	Demolished houses	1	
	Black paper	1	
	Sacrifice	1	
	Blood	2	
	Clock	1	
	Flame	2	
	Total	15	%15
All categories	Total	91	%100

When the categories related to the War of Independence are examined (Table 4), it is seen that the concept of Independence War in general terms refers to the direction of independence (30%). This is followed by the War of Independence categories in terms of national context with 17% and the context of losses with 15%. Quotation examples of the metaphors by the students for the concept of the War of Independence are as follows:

- War of Independence is like a sandglass for me because as time decreases, people who fight like sand grains also decrease.
- War of Independence is like a computer game for me because there is always a winner.
- War of Independence is like an eye for me because it sees everything, but it is very delicate.
- War of Independence is like the sun for me because it was like a sun above us and brought us to the light.
- War of Independence is like an olive branch for me because it always means peace.
- War of Independence is like a foundation for me because we were established after the war of independence.
- War of Independence is like chess for me because its moves were unclear.
- War of Independence is like a tree for me because it's always upright.
- War of Independence is like a flame for me because it burns everywhere.
- War of Independence is like writing for me because those days are unforgettable.
- War of Independence is like a book for me because it is told, but never ends.
- War of Independence is like a waterfall for me because years pass by, but it still continues to flow.

- War of Independence is like a flag for me because it's like spilled blood.
- War of Independence is like water for me because it's gone like water.
- War of Independence is like a group for me because women, men, children, and the elderly fought as a group in War of Independence.
- War of Independence is like a book for me because I never come out of my mind, and I tell everyone.
- War of Independence is like a shadow for me because we always think of it wherever we go.
- War of Independence is like a sacrifice for me because it saw many sacrifices.
- War of Independence is like a football match for me because there is a winner and a loser.
- War of Independence is like an eraser for me because it wiped out bad days.
- War of Independence is like rain for me because it grows around as it rains.

The drawing related to the concept of “War of Independence” prepared from the metaphors of the students is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Drawing to the concept of “War of Independence”

The third and last sub-question of the research is “What are the metaphorical perceptions of the fourth grade students in primary school on Republic?”, and the metaphors given by the students for this sub-question are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: The metaphors created by the students about the phenomenon of Republic

Metaphor	f	Metaphor	f
Justice	2	Stone	5
Jacket	2	National sovereignty	1
Muslimism	1	Balanced scales	4
Turkishness	1	Mountain	1
Bulbul	3	Tooth	1
Compass	1	Innovation	1
History	1	Flag	5
Sandglass	1	Land	2
Bird	1	Basis	3
Number	1	Home	2
Independence	2	Ballpoint pen	1
Layout	1	Freedom	7
Martyt	2	Sun	1
Epic	1	Clock	1
Book	1	Water	3
Erased	3	Concrete	2
Culture	1	Welfare	2
War	1	Gunpowder	1
Shield	1	Homeland	4
Armor	5	Self-confidence	1
Teacher	1	Pencil	1
Bin	1	Democracy	1
Child	1	Window	1
Dove	1	School	1
Happiness	2		
Total		91	

When the Table 5 is investigated, the metaphors developed by the students about the concept of Republic. The most commonly used metaphors are freedom (7), flag (5), armor (5) and stone (5), respectively. Considering the metaphors in Table 6, six categories can be mentioned in general for the concept of Republic. These include Republic in the context of Freedom, Republic in the context of Law, Republic in the context of Protection, Republic in the National context, Republic in the context of Guidance, and Republic in the context of History. The categories prepared by using metaphors are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: The themes (categories) and metaphors related to the phenomenon of Republic

Categories	Metaphors	Number	Percentage (%)
Republic in the context of Freedom			
	Bulbul	3	
	Sandglass	1	
	Bird	1	
	Number	1	
	Independence	2	
	Homeland	4	
	Eraser	3	

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	Child	1	
	Dove	1	
	Happiness	2	
	Window	1	
	Freedom	7	
	Flag	5	
	Welfare	2	
	Water	3	
	National sovereignty	1	
	Total	38	%42
Republic in the context of Law			
	Justice	2	
	Layout	1	
	Democracy	1	
	Innovation	1	
	Balanced scales	4	
	Total	9	%10
Republic in the context of Protection			
	Jacket	2	
	War	1	
	Shield	1	
	Armor	5	
	Self-confidence	1	
	Concrete	2	
	Land	2	
	Basis	3	
	Home	2	
	Mountain	1	
	Stone	5	
	Total	25	%27
Republic in the National context			
	Turkishness	1	
	Martyr	2	
	Tooth	1	
	Total	4	%4
Republic in the context of Guidance			
	Compass	1	
	Teacher	1	
	School	1	
	Sun	1	
	Clock	1	
	Sun	1	
	Total	6	%7
Republic in the context of History			
	History	1	
	Muslimism	1	
	Epic	1	
	Book	1	
	Culture	1	

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	Bin	1	
	Pencil	1	
	Gunpowder	1	
	Ballpoint pen	1	
	Total	9	%10
All categories	Total	91	%100

When the categories related to the phenomenon of the Republic (Table 6) are examined, it is seen that the concept Republic in general terms refers to the direction of freedom (42%). This is followed by 27% in the context of Protection and 10% in the contexts of history-law. Quotation examples of the metaphors by the students for the concept of Republic are as follows:

- Republic is like a number for me because it is an endless beauty like numbers.
- Republic is like a bird for me because it reminds freedom to us, like birds.
- Republic is like an hourglass for me because it decreases over time.
- Republic is like Turkishness for me because republic represents the Turks.
- Republic is like a jacket for me because it always wraps us.
- Republic is like justice for me because the fairest administration is the republic.
- Republic is like a stone for me because it is always strong.
- Republic is like a balanced scales for me because republic is right, justice, and freedom. If the balance strikes, the country collapses.
- Republic is like a mountain for me because it is splendid like a mountain.
- Republic is like a tooth for me because it is very sharp.
- Republic is like land for me because it is very fertile.
- Republic is the basis for me because it's very strong.
- Republic is like a home for me because it always protects me.
- Republic is like a ballpoint pen for me because it never ends.
- Republic is like a compass for me because it leads me.
- Republic is like a bin for me because it contains many things in it.
- Republic is like armor for me because it always protects us.
- Republic is like concrete for me because it keeps the building.
- Republic is like a teacher for me because it taught me so many things.
- Republic is like a window for me because if we open it, it will enlighten everywhere.

The drawing of the concept of "Republic" prepared based on the metaphors of the students is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Drawing of the concept of “Republic”

4. Conclusion and Discussion

In this present study, the metaphoric perceptions of the fourth grade students in primary school about the concepts of Atatürk, Republic, and War of Independence were investigated. When the opinions of the students are examined, it is clearly concluded that they mentioned the concept of Atatürk mostly as hero, star, savior, and leader. In general, the students consider Atatürk as a person who saved the country, found the country, and guided the people. One of the factors that affect the perceptions of the students is the texts in the student books in schools. When we look at the 4th grade course and workbook (MEB, 2017), it is seen that the theme of Atatürk, which is the second theme, includes the caretakers of republic, the childhood of Atatürk, Atatürk in War of Independence, the only person who has not lost his hope, and the texts of national sovereignty and national struggle. When the contents of the texts are examined in general terms, referring to the wars that Atatürk experienced during the war of liberation, they generally refer to the wars and information about his military characteristics. In this context, it is expected that students will come to the forefront of Atatürk's savior and military qualities. Sucu (2011), in his study on elementary school students, concluded that the perceptions of the students on Atatürk were more influential in their perceptions of Atatürk, that their attitudes towards Atatürk and Atatürkism were high, and that they believed that if Atatürk were there, everything would be different. What is common in the majority of students is the emphasis on the military identity of Atatürk. In this context, the research contains similar elements as the present study. In his study, Elmas (2013) concluded that the perceptions of the students on Atatürk were in the form of “*the lender, the savior, and the leader*”. In addition, in the

same study, in terms of the question "If Atatürk were alive, would there be any difference in your life?", it was concluded that students generally gave positive answers, and they expressed their opinions about the difference. Bayar (2009, p. 19) Atatürk was a "great man, great men are like mountains, and as you move away from them, they are defined as majesty". Özgül (2016) conceptualizes Atatürk as "a leader, courageous and enduring (infinite)". In his book, "Who is Atatürk? Atatürk's Nationalism", Palazoğlu (2006) described Atatürk in general as "unafraid, patriotic and mighty". Kongar (2006) refers to the "genius and revolutionary features" of Atatürk. In general, the metaphors related to Atatürk in the literature and the answers given by students are similar.

Students generally describe War of Independence as freedom and independence. Since War of Independence is a struggle for independence by the Turkish people and a victory against the enemies, the opinions of the students are at the expected level. Looking at the metaphors of the War of Independence, 15% of the students mentioned the negative points of the war. The views of the students about the losses are "War of Independence is like a sandglass for me because as time decreases, people who fight like sand grains also decrease.", "War of Independence is like a computer game for me because there is always a winner.", "War of Independence is like an eye for me because it sees everything, but it is very delicate.", "War of Independence is like a flame for me because it burns everywhere.", "War of Independence is like a flag for me because it's like spilled blood.", and "War of Independence is like a football match for me because there is a winner and a loser.". Considering the views, it is noteworthy that the students mentioned the negative aspects of the war, and although War of Independence was won by the Turks, understanding of "There was no winner in the war." is remarkable. It is seen that the metaphors used in the concept of republic are respectively freedom (7), flag (5), armor (5), and stone (5). The students see War of Independence as the independence of the country and accept this as a phenomenon revealing the concept of homeland. As a matter of fact, it is seen that the concepts created for War of Independence can be said for the homeland. In his study, Türküresin (2018) concluded that the perceptions of the students in secondary school on the concept of homeland are positive and that they have awareness about homeland love. In their research, Gömleksiz and Öner (2016) investigated the metaphors of secondary school students about the concept of homeland and concluded that the students mostly developed "home" and "family" metaphors for the concept of homeland. When the metaphors generated by the students in the research are examined, it is comprehended that they have positive thoughts about the concept of homeland, that they feel safe within the borders of the homeland, that they realize the importance of the homeland, and that they think that homeland should be protected.

When the metaphors were examined, the republic was discussed in the context of freedom and protection. The students referred to the mission to protect the rights and laws of republic and the consequence of the independence of the people. In addition, as a result of such views as "Republic is like a number for me because it is an endless beauty like numbers.", it is observed that students have full beliefs in the republic and that they have a feeling that a life without a republic is unbearable. It is noteworthy that a student

mentioned that “*Republic is like a balanced scales for me because republic is right, justice, and freedom. If the balance strikes, the country collapses*”. A student likens Republic, a form of government with different opinions and ideas, as a bin by stating that Republic contains many things in it. Such views as “*Republic is like an hourglass for me because it decreases over time*” indicates that the students have a pessimistic belief for the future. Although the studies on the concept of Republic cannot be achieved in the literature, when the studies on the concept of democracy which is a similar concept was examined, Sadık and Sarı (2012) concluded that the students in primary school perceive democracy as a synonymous form of administration with the concepts of equality, freedom and justice. Duman (2014), in his study with pre-service teachers, revealed that the pre-service teachers identified democracy through the concepts of freedom and equality.

6. Recommendations

- In this research, metaphorical perceptions of the students on Atatürk, Republic, and War of Independence were investigated. The results are the opinions of the students, and the reasons for these opinions are not known. In this context, the reasons for these perceptions can be reveal through in-depth interviews.
- Within the scope of values education, studies on the determination of the metaphorical perception on the national and cultural values can be carried out in a quantitative context.
- Longitudinal studies on the inclusion of the perceptions of the students on these concepts in time can be conducted.
- Metaphoric perception differentiation among the grade levels can be examined, and in-depth researches about the reasons for this can be studied.
- The reasons constituting metaphorical perceptions of the students on the concepts can be examined, and in this context, family and teacher status can also be investigated.
- Relational screening studies on the variables affecting metaphoric perceptions of the students can be conducted. The studies on such status as gender, age, family education level, or reading can be exemplified.

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